

**PROBLEMS OF EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGISMS:
LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS**

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Abstract: The article provides a linguistic analysis of the problems of equivalence of phraseologisms in translation. Factors such as semantic holisticness, cultural differences and polysemy are considered in detail, and methods of equivalence (full correspondence, partial modification, no correspondence) and translation strategies (paraphrase, omission, modulation) are analyzed. Translation problems are highlighted using examples from Uzbek, English, Arabic and German, and issues of dynamic and functional equivalence are discussed based on the theories of Yu. Nayda and Vinay-Darbelnet. The results help to ensure cultural adaptation and semantic accuracy in translation practice, shed light on the global interaction between languages and contribute to the development of translation linguistics.

Keywords: Phraseologisms, translation, equivalence, linguistic analysis, semantic gaps, cultural differences, polysemy, dynamic equivalence, idiomatic units, functional compatibility, paraphrase, omission, modulation, stylistic equivalence, pragmatic equivalence, national realities, transliteration, descriptive methods, global interaction, translation theory.

**FRAZELOGIZMLARNING TARJIMADA EKVALENTLIK MUAMMOLARI:
LINGVISTIK TAHLIL**

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Anotatsiya: Maqola frazeologizmlarning tarjimada ekvivalentlik muammolarini lingvistik tahlil qiladi. Semantik holistiklik, madaniy farqlar va polisemiya kabi omillar batafsil ko'rib chiqilib, ekvivalensiya usullari (to'liq moslik, qisman o'zgartirish, hech qanday moslik) va tarjima strategiyalari (parafraza, omissiya, modulyatsiya) tahlil etiladi. O'zbek, ingliz, arab va nemis tillaridagi misollar orqali tarjima muammolari yoritiladi, shuningdek, Yu. Nayda va Vinay-Darbelnet nazariyalari asosida dinamik va funksional ekvivalensiya masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Natijalar tarjimonlik amaliyotida madaniy moslashuv va semantik aniqlikni ta'minlashga yordam berib, tillar o'rtasidagi global o'zaro ta'sirni yoritadi va tarjima lingvistikasining rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Frazeologizmlar, tarjima, ekvivalentlik, lingvistik tahlil, semantik bo'shliqlar, madaniy farqlar, polisemiya, dinamik ekvivalensiya, idiomatik birliklar, funksional moslik, parafraza, omissiya, modulyatsiya, stilistik ekvivalensiya, pragmatik ekvivalensiya, milliy realiyalar, transliteratsiya, deskriptiv usullar, global o'zaro ta'sir, tarjimonlik nazariyasi.

**ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЭКВИВАЛЕНТНОСТИ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМОВ ПРИ ПЕРЕВОДЕ:
ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ**

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Аннотация: В статье представлен лингвистический анализ проблем эквивалентности фразеологизмов при переводе. Подробно рассматриваются такие факторы, как семантическая целостность, культурные различия и полисемия, анализируются методы эквивалентности (полное соответствие, частичное изменение, отсутствие соответствия) и стратегии перевода (парафраз, опущение, модуляция). Проблемы перевода освещаются на примерах из узбекского, английского, арабского и немецкого языков, а вопросы динамической и функциональной эквивалентности рассматриваются с опорой на теории Ю. Найды и Винай-Дарбелнета. Полученные результаты способствуют обеспечению культурной адаптации и семантической точности в практике перевода, проливают свет на глобальное взаимодействие языков и вносят вклад в развитие лингвистики перевода.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, перевод, эквивалентность, лингвистический анализ, семантические пробелы, культурные различия, полисемия, динамическая эквивалентность, идиоматические единицы, функциональная совместимость, парафраз, пропуск, модуляция, стилистическая эквивалентность, прагматическая эквивалентность, национальные реалии, транслитерация, описательные методы, глобальное взаимодействие, теория перевода.

Translation is an important area of linguistics, and the translation of phraseologisms is fraught with difficulties due to national cultural characteristics and semantic holisticness. The problems of equivalence in the translation of phraseological units based on the classification of V.V. Vinogradov shed light on the global interaction of language. This article aims to enrich the theory of translation by analyzing the semantic and cultural equivalence of phraseologisms in translation.

The problems of equivalence of phraseologisms in translation are a complex area of linguistics from the point of view of linguistic analysis, and it is difficult to achieve complete equivalence due to their semantic holisticness and cultural dependence. Phraseological units, according to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov, are divided into idiomatic units, associations and compounds, and the fact that they exceed the sum of the meanings of their components requires semantic, stylistic and cultural equivalence in translation. For example, the literal translation of the English phraseologism “kick the bucket” (to die) into Uzbek is absurd and is solved by functional equivalence (“to surrender one’s life”), which indicates cultural and semantic gaps. Equivalence problems are divided into groups such as semantic gaps, cultural differences and polysemy, leading to dynamic equivalence (natural translation); units such as the English “spill the beans” (to reveal the secret) lose their nuances in Arabic translation due to the difference in cultural metaphors. In linguistic analysis, the national characteristics of phraseologisms are important, they reflect folk wisdom and imagination, and require preservation of style in translation; for example, “too many cooks spoil the broth” is consistent with the Uzbek “oshpaz k'p b'lsa osh buziladi”, but the difference in cultural imagery can lose style. In translation, equivalence methods include full correspondence (“lose one's head” – “boshini yo'qotmoq”), partial substitution (“get out of bed on the wrong foot” – “chap yoni bilan turmoq”), and no correspondence (“when pigs fly” – “tuyaning dumi yerga tekkanda”), taking into account the idiomatic nature. The problems in translating idiomatic collocations are divided into three groups: cultural dependence (the incompatibility of English sports metaphors with Arabic Bedouin life), semantic transparency differences (when English opaque units pass into Arabic descriptive units), and context dependence, which forces the translator to paraphrase, omit, or linguistically adapt. Phraseologisms with a food component (English “baker's dozen” - 13, there is no Uzbek equivalent) are analyzed on the basis of the Bible and literature, revealing cultural differences; in translation, they are solved by addition or reduction (Yu. Nayda's theory), since phraseologisms are the product of ethnic creativity. The translation of phraseologisms in the Uzbek language is based on dictionary and contextual analysis, and national realities (“cold war”) are resolved by transliteration or descriptive methods, which requires a linguistic approach that takes into account internal and external factors of the language. The analysis of phraseologisms in German and Uzbek shows the relationships of synonymy, antonymy and variant, classifying equivalence: full equivalence (congruence of meaning, form and stylistic features) and similar phraseologisms (semantically and stylistically close, but different in image or basis). In translation, it is important to preserve the contextual meaning, emotional-expressive and stylistic features, since in the absence of equivalence, semantic distortions occur. The main problems and equivalence issues in the translation of idiomatic collocations in Uzbek

and English are manifested through structural differences (English verb-noun combinations and Uzbek noun-noun or adjective-noun pairs) and semantic gaps (full equivalence for universal concepts, for example, “time is money” – “time – money”). Cultural differences play an important role in the translation of phraseologisms; For example, the Uzbek phrase “full stomach, empty heart” (material satisfaction, but spiritual dissatisfaction) does not exist in English and requires cultural adaptation. Translation methods (modulation, equivalence according to the theory of Vinay and Darbelnet) provide semantic, stylistic and pragmatic equivalence, which sheds light on the global interaction of language. The problems of equivalence of phraseological units in translation are solved through cultural adaptation and semantic accuracy and remain an urgent issue of linguistics. Solving these problems improves translation practice and strengthens the cultural bridge between languages.

List of used literature

1. Jamolkhonov H. The current Uzbek literary language. Tashkent: Fan, 2004.
2. Sharipova O., Yuldoshev I. Fundamentals of Linguistics. Tashkent: National University of Uzbekistan, 2010.
3. Turaboyeva L. On the study of phraseological issues in the Uzbek language. Karakalpakstan State University, 2022.
4. Ermatov I. Current Uzbek literary language (Lexicology, phraseology, lexicography). Tashkent: Scienceweb, 2023.
5. Yusupova B. Phraseology of the Karakalpak language. Tashkent: UzResearchers, 2023.